

Community Decision-Making in Study Planning and Implementation

Research Phase	Informing	Consultation	Partnership	Community Ownership
Research questions or focus of the research	Research is based on funding priorities.	The Community provides input in identifying locally relevant issues.	Researchers and the Community identify issues of importance.	The Community identifies issues of greatest importance.
Research design	Researchers design the study based entirely on scientific rigor and feasibility without the input of the Community. Researchers inform the Community of the plan.	Researchers share the design with the Community and ask for feedback.	Researchers work with the Community to ensure the study design is tailored to the cultural and social context.	The Community is intimately involved with the study design.
Instrument design	Researchers adopt or adapt instruments from other studies or create them. Researchers share instruments with the Community, but not for feedback.	Researchers develop instruments and share them with the Community for feedback.	Researchers codevelop instruments with the Community to ensure alignment with the cultural and social context.	The Community leads creation of data collection instruments and grounds them in the cultural and social context.
Data collection	Researchers or individuals with no connection to the Community conduct data collection.	The Community provides input on aspects of data collection but is not involved with data collection.	The Community is involved in some aspects of data collection.	The Community conducts data collection, to the extent possible based on available skill sets. The focus is on capacity building.
Analysis and Interpretation	Researchers own the data, conduct analysis, interpret findings, and develop recommendations.	Researchers share results of the analysis with the Community for comments.	Researchers and the Community work together to interpret results and develop recommendations.	The Community leads analysis, interpretation of results, and development of recommendations, with support from researchers.
Dissemination	Researchers give and direct results towards the main client.	Researchers disseminate results to the Community.	The Community assists researchers in identifying appropriate formats and venues for disseminating results.	The Community leads the creation of deliverables and decides on dissemination venues.

Note. "Community" represents research participants and/or individuals and communities most affected by the research.

Framework developed using the following resources:

Arnstein, S. R. (1969). A ladder of citizen participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4), 216–224.
 Nitsch, M., Waldherr, K., Denk, E., Griebler, U., Marent, B., & Forster, R. (2013). Participation by different stakeholders in participatory evaluation of health promotion: A literature review. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 40, 42–54.

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